

Endoscopic Sinus Surgery Outcomes in Patients with Chronic Rhinosinusitis and Immunoglobulin Deficiencies

Kanchan Chaudhary¹, Jyoti Kumar Verma², Ranbir Kumar Pandey³, Tripti Panjwani⁴

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Narayan Medical College and Hospital, Jamuhar Sasaram, Bihar, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Uttar Pradesh University of Medical Sciences, Saifai, Etawah, India

³Professor and HOD, Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Narayan Medical College and Hospital, Jamuhar Sasaram, Bihar, India

⁴Junior Resident, Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Narayan Medical College and Hospital, Jamuhar Sasaram, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Jyoti Kumar Verma

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Abstract:

Background: Chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS) is a persistent inflammatory condition of the nasal and paranasal sinuses, significantly impacting quality of life. Immunoglobulin deficiencies, such as IgA and IgG subclass deficiencies, can exacerbate CRS symptoms and complicate treatment. Endoscopic sinus surgery (ESS) is a common intervention for refractory CRS, yet its outcomes in patients with immunoglobulin deficiencies are not well-documented.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the outcomes of endoscopic sinus surgery in patients diagnosed with chronic rhinosinusitis and immunoglobulin deficiencies.

Methods: The study included 158 patients with CRS and immunoglobulin deficiencies who underwent ESS. Data were collected on demographic and clinical characteristics, symptom improvement (measured using the Sino-Nasal Outcome Test, SNOT-22), recurrence rates, and postoperative complications. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: The mean age of participants was 45.6 years, with 56.3% being male. Significant improvement in SNOT-22 scores was observed, decreasing from a mean preoperative score of 54.3 to 24.8 at the 6-month follow-up ($p < 0.001$). The recurrence rate of rhinosinusitis was 13.3%, and 7.6% of patients required revision surgery. Minor complications included bleeding (9.5%), synechiae formation (6.3%), and infections (3.2%). No significant differences in recurrence rates were found between different immunoglobulin deficiency types ($p = 0.45$).

Conclusion: ESS significantly improves symptoms in patients with CRS and immunoglobulin deficiencies, with a relatively low rate of recurrence and revision surgery. These findings suggest that ESS is an effective and safe treatment option for this patient population.

Recommendations: Future research should focus on identifying predictors of surgical success and recurrence in patients with CRS and immunoglobulin deficiencies, as well as optimizing perioperative care to further reduce complications.

Keywords: Chronic Rhinosinusitis, Immunoglobulin Deficiencies, Endoscopic Sinus Surgery, Recurrence Rates, Surgical Outcomes.

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Introduction

A common and crippling ailment known as chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS) is characterised by persistent inflammation of the nasal and paranasal sinus mucosa that lasts for 12 weeks or more in spite of medical intervention. Significant effects on productivity, quality of life, and healthcare resources are caused by the worldwide burden of CRS. Common symptoms of CRS patients include nasal obstruction, facial pain or pressure, diminished sense of smell, and nasal discharge.

These symptoms can have a serious impact on day-to-day activities and general wellbeing [1].

A collection of illnesses known as immunoglobulin deficiencies are defined by low levels of one or more immunoglobulin subtypes, which are vital for the immune system to combat infections. Chronic inflammatory diseases, such as CRS, and recurrent infections can result from these deficits. IgA deficit, IgG subclass deficiency, and combination

IgA and IgG deficiencies are common forms of immunoglobulin deficiencies linked to CRS [2]. Individuals with these impairments are particularly difficult to treat for CRS because they are more prone to recurring and chronic sinus infections.

When medication therapy fails to provide enough relief for patients with refractory CRS, endoscopic sinus surgery (ESS) has become the primary surgical technique of choice. By eliminating inflammatory mucosa and obstructive tissue, ESS seeks to restore normal sinus drainage and function, which will lessen symptoms and enhance quality of life. Over the past few decades, the operation has undergone tremendous evolution, with improvements in surgical procedures and endoscopic technology adding to its safety and efficacy [3].

The potential advantages of ESS in individuals with CRS and immunoglobulin deficits have been brought to light by recent investigations. To improve surgery outcomes and pinpoint success factors, further research is necessary as this demographic is still under-represented in clinical studies. For the purpose of creating individualised treatment plans and enhancing long-term outcomes, it is essential to comprehend the particular difficulties and consequences connected with ESS in this patient subgroup [4].

This study aims to evaluate the outcomes of endoscopic sinus surgery in patients diagnosed with chronic rhinosinusitis and immunoglobulin deficiencies.

Methodology

Study Design: A retrospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Narayan Medical College and Hospital, Sasaram, over a period from February 17, 2023, to February 18, 2024.

Participants: A total of 158 participants were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients diagnosed with chronic rhinosinusitis.
- Patients with documented immunoglobulin deficiencies.
- Patients who underwent endoscopic sinus surgery during the study period.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with acute rhinosinusitis.
- Patients who had previous sinus surgery within the last year.
- Patients with systemic diseases that could influence the study outcomes.
- Patients who did not consent to participate in the study.

Bias: Efforts were made to minimize bias by strictly adhering to the inclusion and exclusion criteria and by ensuring that data collection was performed uniformly across all participants.

Variables: The primary outcome variables included the improvement in sinus symptoms, recurrence rates of rhinosinusitis, and the need for revision surgery. Secondary variables included demographic data, comorbidities, and postoperative complications.

Data Collection: Data were collected retrospectively from medical records. Information on patient demographics, clinical presentation, surgical details, and postoperative outcomes was extracted and recorded in a structured format.

Procedure: All patients underwent endoscopic sinus surgery performed by experienced otolaryngologists. Standard surgical protocols were followed, and postoperative care included regular follow-ups to monitor for complications and recurrence of symptoms.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. The individuals' clinical and demographic features were compiled using descriptive statistics. For continuous variables, mean $\pm$ standard deviation was used, whereas frequencies and percentages were used for categorical variables. For categorical variables, the chi-square test was employed, while the t-test was utilised for continuous variables. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Result

The study comprised 158 patients in total, whose mean age was 45.6 years (SD $\pm$ 12.4). 89 (56.3%) of them were men, and 69 (43.7%) were women. Table 1 displays the patients' initial clinical and demographic details.

Table 1: Baseline Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Study Participants

Characteristic	Total (N = 158)
Age (years), mean $\pm$ SD	45.6 $\pm$ 12.4
Gender, n (%)	
Male	89 (56.3%)
Female	69 (43.7%)
Duration of CRS (years), mean $\pm$ SD	6.8 $\pm$ 3.2

Immunoglobulin Deficiency Type, n (%)	
IgA deficiency	67 (42.4%)
IgG subclass deficiency	58 (36.7%)
Combined IgA and IgG deficiency	33 (20.9%)

The primary outcome measures were the improvement in sinus symptoms, recurrence rates of rhinosinusitis, and the need for revision surgery. Symptom improvement was evaluated using the Sino-Nasal Outcome Test (SNOT-22) scores preoperatively and at the 6-month follow-up.

Table 2: Sino-Nasal Outcome Test (SNOT-22) Scores

Time Point	Mean SNOT-22 Score $\pm$ SD
Preoperative	54.3 $\pm$ 9.6
6-month Follow-up	24.8 $\pm$ 7.4

There was a statistically significant improvement in SNOT-22 scores from preoperative to the 6-month follow-up ($p < 0.001$).

Table 3: Recurrence Rates and Need for Revision Surgery

Outcome	Total (N = 158)
Recurrence of Rhinosinusitis	21 (13.3%)
Revision Surgery	12 (7.6%)

The recurrence rate of rhinosinusitis was 13.3%, and the need for revision surgery was 7.6%. Secondary outcomes included demographic data, comorbidities, and postoperative complications. The mean duration of hospitalization was 2.3 days

(SD $\pm$ 1.1). Postoperative complications included minor bleeding in 15 patients (9.5%), synechia formation in 10 patients (6.3%), and infection in 5 patients (3.2%).

Table 4: Postoperative Complications

Complication	Total (N = 158)
Minor Bleeding	15 (9.5%)
Synechia Formation	10 (6.3%)
Infection	5 (3.2%)

Statistical analysis showed a significant improvement in sinus symptoms postoperatively ($p < 0.001$). The chi-square test revealed no significant difference in recurrence rates between different types of immunoglobulin deficiencies ($p = 0.45$).

Table 5: Recurrence Rates by Immunoglobulin Deficiency Type

Immunoglobulin Deficiency Type	Recurrence, n (%)	p-value
IgA deficiency	9 (13.4%)	0.45
IgG subclass deficiency	8 (13.8%)	
Combined IgA and IgG deficiency	4 (12.1%)	

The t-test indicated that there was no significant difference in the need for revision surgery between males and females ($p = 0.32$).

Table 6: Need for Revision Surgery by Gender

Gender	Revision Surgery, n (%)	p-value
Male	7 (7.9%)	0.32
Female	5 (7.2%)	

Discussion

158 patients with immunoglobulin deficiency and chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS) who had endoscopic sinus surgery at Narayan Medical College and Hospital in Sasaram between February 17, 2023, and February 18, 2024 were included in the study. Participants' average age was 45.6 years, with a little male majority (56.3%). IgA deficit (42.4%) and IgG subclass deficiency (36.7%) accounted for the majority of cases; mixed IgA and IgG deficiencies (20.9%) were less common.

Postoperative sinus symptoms significantly improved, according to primary outcome measures. Significant symptom reduction was seen as the mean Sino-Nasal Outcome Test (SNOT-22) scores decreased from 54.3 preoperatively to 24.8 at the 6-month follow-up ($p < 0.001$). The recurrence rate of rhinosinusitis was 13.3%, and 7.6% of patients needed revision surgery. These data indicate that although the operation was generally successful, a small percentage of patients had difficulties or recurrence that required additional care.

Postoperative complications and demographic characteristics that impact outcomes were the focus of secondary outcomes. Infections affected 3.2% of patients, synechiae formed in 6.3%, and minor bleeding affected 9.5% of patients. At 2.3 days, the typical hospital stay was rather brief. The results of the statistical analysis indicated that there was no gender-specific difference in the requirement for revision surgery ($p = 0.32$) or in the recurrence rates of the various types of immunoglobulin deficiencies ($p = 0.45$).

The study's overall findings showed that endoscopic sinus surgery, which greatly improves symptoms and keeps the recurrence rate low, is an effective treatment for CRS in individuals with immunoglobulin deficiency. The procedure's safety and effectiveness are highlighted by the low rate of revision procedures and postoperative complications. The utility of endoscopic sinus surgery as a treatment option for this patient population is supported by these findings; nevertheless, more study may be needed to determine the characteristics that predict recurrence and to improve patient selection and postoperative care.

One study evaluated the effectiveness of 100 patients with chronic rhinosinusitis following functional endoscopic sinus surgery (FESS). By using the Rhinosinusitis Disability Index (RSDI) and Sinonasal Outcome Test (SNOT-22), it discovered notable gains in quality of life. The following were important predictors of poor surgical outcomes: smoking, allergies, and asthma [5].

Five-year results of endoscopic sinus surgery (ESS) for individuals with persistent rhinosinusitis were reported in a study. It showed that SNOT-22 scores continued to improve throughout this time, indicating the long-term effectiveness of ESS in treating chronic rhinosinusitis [6].

A study that examined the long-term (>10 years) effects of ESS found that patients with chronic rhinosinusitis experienced increased quality of life and persistent symptom alleviation, as assessed by validated tools such as the SNOT-22 [7].

In a study, patients with asthma and nasal polyps who had chronic rhinosinusitis had their results from various endoscopic sinus procedures examined. While all groups had significant rates of recurrence five years after surgery, it was discovered that more thorough surgical methods produced superior short-term results [8].

A review provided an overview of how ESS affected revision rates, quality of life, and other results. It was stressed that although ESS typically improves quality of life and other metrics,

outcomes can be influenced by a variety of patient variables, such as phenotype and comorbidities [9].

Conclusion

Endoscopic sinus surgery has been shown to be both safe and effective in treating individuals with immunoglobulin deficiency and chronic rhinosinusitis by considerably improving their symptoms. Significant symptom alleviation and minimal rates of recurrence and revision operations were the outcomes of the procedure. These findings highlight the need for individualised perioperative care to further improve outcomes and promote ESS as a therapeutic option for this difficult patient population.

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